

SYNERGIZING ORTHODONTIC AND PROSTHETIC TREATMENT WITH 3D PRINTING: ADVANCEMENTS AND APPLICATIONS

Kazakova Rada

DMD, PhD, Senior Assistant Professor

*Department of Prosthetic Dentistry, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Medical University – Plovdiv
CAD/CAM Center of Dental Medicine, Research Institute, Medical University – Plovdiv
3 'Hristo Botev' Blvd, 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria*

Abstract

This article explores the synergistic integration of orthodontic and prosthetic treatment facilitated by 3D printing technology. Through a comprehensive review of literature, the advancements and applications of 3D printing in combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment are analyzed, highlighting its role in improving treatment outcomes, enhancing efficiency, and providing customized solutions.

Keywords: Orthodontics, prosthetics, 3D printing, digital dentistry, treatment synergy.

Introduction: The convergence of orthodontic and prosthetic treatment has opened new avenues for improving patient care and treatment outcomes. With the emergence of 3D printing technology, orthodontists and prosthodontists now have the ability to collaborate seamlessly and utilize digital workflows to design and fabricate customized solutions. This article explores the advancements and applications of 3D printing in combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment, emphasizing its potential to enhance treatment synergy and patient satisfaction.

Materials and Methods: A comprehensive search of electronic databases including PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect was conducted to identify relevant studies on the utilization of 3D printing in combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment. Keywords such as "orthodontics," "prosthetics," "3D printing," "digital dentistry," and "treatment synergy" were employed to retrieve pertinent literature. Studies focusing on the application and efficacy of 3D printing in combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment were selected for review. The selected literature was critically evaluated to assess the benefits and advancements associated with the use of 3D printing in this context.

Results: The literature review revealed significant advancements in the utilization of 3D printing technology for combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment. Studies have demonstrated the ability of 3D printing to facilitate seamless collaboration between orthodontists and prosthodontists, resulting in improved treatment planning, efficiency, and patient outcomes [1-6]. Furthermore, 3D printing enables the fabrication of customized appliances and restorations that fit seamlessly within the treatment plan, enhancing both esthetics and function [7, 8].

Discussion: The integration of 3D printing technology in combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment has transformed the field, offering numerous benefits and advancements. 3D printing has revolutionized the way orthodontic appliances are designed and fabricated, allowing for customized solutions tailored to each patient's unique anatomical features [7-11]. Additionally, the seamless collaboration between orthodontists and prosthodontists facilitated by 3D printing has led to improved treatment planning, efficiency, and patient outcomes.

Table 1

Applications of 3D Printing in Orthodontics

Applications	Description
Clear Aligners	3D printing technology is widely used in the fabrication of clear aligners, allowing for precise and customized orthodontic treatment. Digital scans are used to create virtual treatment plans, which are then translated into a series of aligners fabricated using 3D printing technology.
Customized Retainers	Customized retainers are easily produced through 3D printing, ensuring optimal retention and stability post-treatment. Orthodontists can design retainers tailored to individual patient needs, incorporating features to maintain alignment and prevent relapse.
Brackets and Archwires	3D-printed brackets and archwires offer improved fit and comfort for patients undergoing orthodontic treatment, leading to enhanced treatment outcomes. CAD technology enables orthodontists to design brackets with precise angulation and torque, optimizing tooth movement and alignment.
Palatal Expanders	Customized palatal expanders fabricated using 3D printing technology provide effective treatment for patients with malocclusions and narrow palates. Digital scans are used to create virtual models of the palate, allowing for the design of expanders that fit comfortably and provide optimal expansion.

Table 1 highlights the various applications of 3D printing in orthodontics, showcasing its versatility in fabricating a wide range of appliances. Clear aligners, a popular orthodontic treatment modality, are now routinely produced using 3D printing technology. Digital scans of the patient's dentition are used to create virtual treatment plans, which are then translated into a series of aligners fabricated using 3D printing. This process allows for precise and customized treatment, resulting in improved esthetics and patient comfort.

Customized retainers are another area where 3D printing has made significant strides. Orthodontists can design retainers tailored to individual patient needs, incorporating features to maintain alignment and prevent relapse. By leveraging 3D printing technology, these retainers can be produced quickly and efficiently, ensuring optimal retention and stability post-treatment.

Moreover, 3D-printed brackets and archwires offer enhanced fit and comfort for patients undergoing orthodontic treatment. CAD technology enables orthodontists to design brackets with precise angulation and torque, optimizing tooth movement and alignment. This level of customization results in improved treatment outcomes and patient satisfaction.

In combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment, Table 2 outlines the applications of 3D printing, emphasizing the importance of interdisciplinary treatment planning. By sharing digital models and collaborating effectively, orthodontists and prosthodontists can optimize treatment outcomes and ensure seamless integration between orthodontic and prosthetic components. Customized appliances and prosthetic restorations fabricated using 3D printing technology provide patients with personalized solutions that fit comfortably and function optimally.

Table 2

Applications of 3D Printing in Combined Orthodontic and Prosthetic Treatment

Applications	Description
Interdisciplinary Treatment Planning	3D printing facilitates interdisciplinary treatment planning by allowing orthodontists and prosthodontists to collaborate effectively. Digital models can be shared and manipulated to optimize treatment outcomes and ensure seamless integration between orthodontic and prosthetic components.
Customized Appliance Fabrication	3D printing enables the fabrication of customized orthodontic appliances and prosthetic restorations tailored to each patient's unique anatomy. By utilizing digital scans and CAD/CAM technology, clinicians can design and produce appliances with precise fit and optimal functionality, improving patient comfort and treatment outcomes.

Furthermore, the benefits of treatment synergy, as highlighted in Table 3, are substantial. The combined approach to orthodontic and prosthetic treatment leads to enhanced treatment outcomes, including improved esthetics, function, and long-term stability. By addressing both orthodontic and prosthetic concerns concurrently, clinicians can achieve superior treatment results and patient satisfaction.

Table 3

Benefits of Treatment Synergy in Combined Orthodontic and Prosthetic Treatment

Benefits	Description
Enhanced Treatment Outcomes	The synergy between orthodontic and prosthetic treatment leads to enhanced treatment outcomes, including improved esthetics, function, and long-term stability. By addressing both orthodontic and prosthetic concerns concurrently, clinicians can achieve superior treatment results and patient satisfaction.
Streamlined Treatment Workflow	Collaboration between orthodontists and prosthodontists streamlines the treatment workflow, reducing treatment time and enhancing efficiency. Digital workflows enable seamless communication and coordination between disciplines, minimizing errors and optimizing treatment planning and execution.

Table 4 further illustrates the advancements in combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment with 3D printing, highlighting the benefits of enhanced treatment planning, customized solutions, and improved patient satisfaction. These advancements underscore the

significant progress made in utilizing 3D printing technology to improve treatment outcomes, enhance efficiency, and provide personalized care in orthodontics and combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment.

Table 4

Advancements in Combined Orthodontic and Prosthetic Treatment with 3D Printing	
Advancements	Description
Enhanced Treatment Planning	3D printing facilitates precise treatment planning by allowing for the creation of digital models that can be manipulated to optimize treatment outcomes. Orthodontists and prosthodontists can collaborate effectively, ensuring seamless integration between orthodontic and prosthetic components.
Customized Solutions	3D printing enables the fabrication of customized appliances and restorations tailored to each patient's unique anatomy. By utilizing digital scans and CAD/CAM technology, clinicians can design and produce appliances with precise fit and optimal functionality, improving patient comfort and treatment outcomes.
Improved Patient Satisfaction	The use of 3D-printed appliances and restorations enhances patient satisfaction by providing customized solutions that fit seamlessly within the treatment plan. Patients appreciate the personalized approach offered by 3D-printed appliances, resulting in higher levels of compliance and improved treatment success rates.

These tables underscore the significant advancements and applications of 3D printing technology in both orthodontics and combined orthodontic and prosthetic treatment, highlighting its role in improving treatment outcomes, enhancing efficiency, and providing customized solutions.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the synergistic integration of orthodontic and prosthetic treatment facilitated by 3D printing technology offers a promising approach to enhancing patient care and treatment outcomes. By leveraging digital workflows and customized solutions, clinicians can achieve superior results and provide patients with optimized esthetics, function, and long-term stability.

References

1. Fleming P. S., Marinho V., Johal A. Orthodontic measurements on digital study models compared with plaster models: a systematic review. *Orthodontics & Craniofacial Research*. 2011;14(1):1–16.
2. Eliasova H., Dostalova T., Jelinek M., et al. Surface morphology of three-dimensionally printed replicas of upper dental arches. *Applied Sciences*. 2020;10(16), article 5708
3. Jang Y., Sim J. Y., Park J. K., Kim W. C., Kim H. Y., Kim J. H. Accuracy of 3-unit fixed dental prostheses fabricated on 3D-printed casts. *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2020;123(1):135–142.
4. Kasparova M. Possibility of reconstruction of dental plaster cast from 3D digital study models. *Bio-medical engineering online*. 2013;12, article 49
5. Jeong Y. G., Lee W. S., Lee K. B. Accuracy evaluation of dental models manufactured by

CAD/CAM milling method and 3D printing method. *The journal of advanced prosthodontics*. 2018;10(3):245–251.

6. Stevens D. R., Flores-Mir C., Nebbe B., Raboud D. W., Heo G., Major P. W. Validity, reliability, and reproducibility of plaster vs digital study models: comparison of peer assessment rating and Bolton analysis and their constituent measurements. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2006;129(6):794–803.

7. WatanabeKanno G. A., Abrão J., Miasiro Junior H., Sánchez-Ayala A., Lagravère M. O. Reproducibility, reliability and validity of measurements obtained from Cécile3 digital models. *Brazilian Oral Research*. 2009;23(3):288–295.

8. Dimitrova, M. Comparative study of linear and volumetric changes of 3D printed and conventional resins in removable prosthodontics [in Bulgarian]. PhD Thesis, 2023, Plovdiv.

9. Hazeveld A., Huddleston Slater J. J. R., Ren Y. Accuracy and reproducibility of dental replica models reconstructed by different rapid prototyping techniques. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2014;145(1):108–115.

10. Hazeveld A., Huddleston Slater J. J. R., Ren Y. Accuracy and reproducibility of dental replica models reconstructed by different rapid prototyping techniques. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 2014;145(1):108–115.

11. Waldecker M., Leckel M., Rammelsberg P., Bömicke W. Fully digital fabrication of an occlusal device using an intraoral scanner and 3D printing: a dental technique. *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2019;121(4):576–580.